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Blue print of collatz.

We will consider 4 residue classes that will cover all odd numbers.

Every class has some rules of transition.

Let the classes be 1,3,5,7 mod8

Rule for 7mod8 class.

Take any number congruent to 7mod8 to calculate position apply

$P = (n+1)/8$ if p is odd it will feedback into 3mod8 class if P is even it will feedback into 7mod8 class until it becomes odd. To make it odd apply this $3p/2$ until it become odd

Example

Let say p is 4 now apply

$4 \cdot 3/2 = 6$ (p is again even so we will apply this rule again)

$6 \cdot 3/2 = 9$ Now our i is odd.

There is another way to calculate p , let say p is 56 divide 56 with 2 until it becomes odd.

Now $p = 3(\text{times you divide with } 2) \cdot \text{odd number}$

Example 56 ($2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 7$)

$i = 3^3 \cdot 7$

Once p is odd apply this rule.

$P = (3p+1)/2$.. this is your position in the 3mod8 class.

Calculate position in 3mod8 class.

To calculate the position in 3mod8

Take any number congruent to 3mod8

$P = (n+5)/8$

If p is odd function will feed back to 5mod8, if p is even function will feedback to 1mod8 remember function will not loop in itself like it did with 7mod8 class when p was even.

If p is odd calculate $(3n-1)/2$ is position in 5mod8 class

If p is even, calculate $3n/2$ is position in 1mod8 class.

Rules for 1mod8 class

Calculate position take any number congruent to 1mod8

$P = (n+7)/8$

If position in 1mod4 apply $(3n+1)/4$ your position in 1mod8 (this class only loop once in itself so returning number will be 1mod4.

If position is 2mod4 apply $(3n - 2)/4$ position in 7mod8 class.

If position is 3mod4 apply $(3n-1)/4$ position in 5mod8 class

If position is 0mod4 apply $3n/4$ position in 3mod8 class

Rules for 5mod8 class

Calculate position

$P = (n+3)/8$

If position is 3mod4 apply $(n+1)/4$ your position in 5mod8 class if again 3mod4 again apply this rule.

If position is 2mod8 apply $(3n+2)/8$ next position in 5mod8

If position is 4mod8 apply $(3n + 4)/8$ position in 3mod8

If position is $6 \bmod 8$ apply $(3n + 6)/8$ position in $1 \bmod 8$

If position is $0 \bmod 8$ apply $3n/8$ position in $7 \bmod 8$

If $1 \bmod 16$ apply $(3n+13)/16$ position in $1 \bmod 8$ class

If $5 \bmod 16$ apply $(3n + 1)/16$ position in $7 \bmod 8$ class

If $9 \bmod 16$ apply $(3n + 5)/16$ position in $5 \bmod 8$ class

If $13 \bmod 16$ apply $(3n+9)/16$ position in $3 \bmod 8$ class.

Done!!!

Subjected to omission in case of typo.